

Harnessing $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-WS}_2$ nanostructures as efficient energy scaffoldings for photocatalytic hydrogen generation

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ABSTRACT

Two-dimensional (2D) Ti_3C_2 MXene have attracted a lot of attention as frontier materials for the development of effective photocatalysts that can transform solar energy into chemical energy, which is essential for water splitting to produce hydrogen. Here, we use first principle calculations to understand the structural, electronic, and vibrational features of a novel heterostructure comprising a monolayer of tungsten disulfide (WS_2) and titanium carbide (Ti_3C_2) MXene. Our theoretical calculations revealed that the Ti_3C_2 maximizes the interfacial contact area with the WS_2 monolayer creating a strong p - d hybridization for the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure. As a result, a well-constructed Schottky junction is enabled, facilitating an interconnected electron pathway across the interface which is conducive for an efficient photocatalytic performance. Further, the experimentally designed $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure and its photocatalytic activity based on the synergistic action between MXene and WS_2 is investigated. Optical properties calculated are compared with experimental data derived from UV-Visible spectroscopy. The excellent conductivity and stability along with the light absorption in the visible region of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ enhances the photocatalytic performance approaching photocurrent densities of ~ 33 and $120 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ in the HER and OER region, respectively. Overall, the present research not only improves our understanding of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure for an improved photocatalytic activity, but also provides an efficient method toward sustainable hydrogen production.

1. Introduction

In the dynamic field of renewable energy, hydrogen (H_2), often hailed as the “fuel of the future” is emerging as a key component of sustainability and modernization leading to global energy transition. Hydrogen is a clean, abundant and adaptable energy source that has the potential to lessen the reliance on fossil fuels, offering a versatile solution to decarbonize sectors such as transportation, industry, and power generation [1,2]. However, a significant challenge in reaching this objective lies in the efficient production of hydrogen. Despite its abundance, being the most common element in the universe, hydrogen is scarcely available in its pure state. Dihydrogen is usually available in the

form of various compounds like water, hydrocarbons, ammonia, organic compounds and hydrides, among others. Therefore, it is essential to discover efficient, cost-effective and scalable methods for its production. Among several methods employed to produce H_2 , currently, steam methane reforming (SMR), water electrolysis and biomass gasification are the three main strategies, differing notably in terms of their carbon emission profiles [3,4]. Within the spectrum of hydrogen production approaches, harnessing photocatalysts for water splitting emerges as a pivotal solution to address sustainability concerns, steering towards a greener future. This approach further enables the utilization of renewable solar energy to power the splitting of water molecules, producing hydrogen as a clean and eco-friendly fuel [5,6].

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Pioneered by Akira Fujishima and Kenichi Honda [7] in the early 1970s, photocatalytic hydrogen production represents a major turning point in the field of sustainable energy research. Through their innovative work, it was shown that semiconductor photocatalyst, TiO_2 could split water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen upon irradiation with light. Additionally, the wide bandgap (~ 3.2 eV) and rapid recombination of photogenerated electron-hole pairs within TiO_2 , significantly limits the absorption of visible light and hinders the ability to facilitate photo-charge separation, thereby reducing the material effectiveness in photocatalytic activity. Subsequently, researchers have persisted globally in expanding upon Fujishima's findings, developing novel photocatalytic materials aiming to increase efficiency and scalability towards energy conversion.

Over the past decades, a plethora of semiconductors were explored, including metal oxides (CuO , NiO , WO_3 , BiVO_4 , ZnO) [8–11], sulfides (CdS , ZnS , WS_2 , MoS_2 , NiS) [12–16], metal oxynitrides [17,18], nitrides (TiN , TaN , MoN) [19–22] and other semiconductors such as graphitic carbon nitride ($\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$) [23], perovskite materials (SrTiO_3 , BaTiO_3) etc. [24–26], as potential photocatalysts for hydrogen evolution. Among those candidates, two dimensional (2D) materials have emerged as particularly noteworthy in the realm of visible-light photocatalytic water splitting [27]. This strengthened focus on 2D materials stems from their advantageous characteristics such as ultrathin structures, suitable band structure conducive to photocatalysis, exceptional thermal and chemical stability, cost-effectiveness, non-toxicity, high surface area, tunable band structures, rapid charge transport and increased charge separation efficiency [28–30]. Moreover, 2D materials offer possibilities for functionalization and surface engineering, enabling the incorporation of targeted functionalities, customizing their properties to suit specific applications. These properties position 2D materials as promising candidates for advancing the efficiency and sustainability of photocatalytic water splitting processes, thus contributing to the development of clean energy technologies [31,32].

Being a novel family of 2D materials, MXenes, composed of transition metal carbides, nitrides or carbonitrides, have attracted significant research attention since their discovery in 2011 [33]. The remarkable properties of MXenes featuring large surface area, high electrical conductivity, hydrophilic nature, superior mechanical strength and exceptional chemical stability, give rise to a myriad of potential applications in the field of energy conversion and storage such as like batteries [34, 35], supercapacitors [36], solar cells [37], catalytic processes [38,39], sensing technology [40], electromagnetic shielding [41] and biomedical applications [42]. Further, with Gibbs free energy for hydrogen adsorption (ΔG_{H}) being a fundamental metric for assessing catalytic activity, based on theoretical studies, it can be inferred that certain MXenes have nearly zero ΔG_{H} , suggesting their potential as effective catalysts for H_2 production. Due to these exceptional structural, optical and electronic properties, MXenes are widely utilized as co-catalysts for photo-electrochemical applications. Zhong et al. [43] reported that the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene when coupled as co-catalyst with ZnO exhibited a notable improvement in photocurrent density reaching 1.2 mA/cm^2 at $1.23 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ with a photoconversion efficiency of 0.32%. It was observed that the incorporation of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ as a co-catalyst on ZnO resulted in effective mitigation of surface charge recombination and facilitated accelerated charge separation processes. Moreover, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ acted as a sensitizer, thereby augmenting the light-harvesting absorption capabilities of the composite photoanode. In an attempt to gain further insights into the influence of cations on photocatalytic hydrogen production, Mo_2C MXene nanosheets were utilized as co-catalysts with CdS , favoring photocatalytic activity [44]. Recent work by Tekalgne et al. [45] on $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ demonstrated a low onset potential of -150 mV vs RHE with Tafel slope of 62 mV/dec for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Despite showing a good catalytic activity, insights on the interface and the intrinsic relationships among the geometrical structure, electronic structure and the photocatalytic activity of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure are still not easy to derive. Hence, a fundamental

understanding of the electronic band structures is required to design and fabricate heterostructures in a more facile manner, targeting to enhance the photocatalytic performance.

Herein, we study the band alignment, electronic structure and photocatalytic activity of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructures using first principle calculations. Furthermore, the synthesis and detailed characterization of novel photocatalysts for water splitting reaction, i.e. WS_2 and Ti_3C_2 , is presented. The photocatalyst was constructed by forming a hybrid structure composed of two-dimensional WS_2 nanosheets integrated with titanium carbide MXene (Ti_3C_2) nanosheets. The synthesized material was thoroughly characterized using a range of analytical techniques to elucidate its structural, morphological, optical and photo-electrochemical characteristics. The $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure was found to offer large interfacial area and favorable band alignments, thereby facilitating enhanced charge separation and redox kinetics. This research piece establishes a groundwork for development and advancement in the design of novel heterostructure photocatalysts with proper band alignment as shown in Fig. 1.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Optimized structure and electronic band structure

Monolayers of WS_2 and Ti_3C_2 components constitute the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure and the corresponding optimized geometries are shown in Fig. S1 (a–c). The band structure of WS_2 monolayer (Fig. 2a inset), Ti_3C_2 monolayer (Fig. 2b inset) and of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ (Fig. 2c inset) heterostructure were calculated to ascertain their energy differences over their transition from a monolayer to the heterostructure. As it can be seen in Fig. 2a, the monolayer WS_2 features a direct bandgap of 1.81 eV, denoting a semiconducting behaviour [46]. In the case of Ti_3C_2 monolayer as portrayed in Fig. 2b, the top of the valence band maximum and bottom of the conduction band minimum overlap and diverge at the Brillouin zone symmetry point responsible for zero band gap, validating a metallic character [47]. Further, upon construction as a heterostructure, the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ (Fig. 2c) displayed a distinct band structure as compared to the individual monolayer components WS_2 and Ti_3C_2 , where the bands are denser in the valence and conduction bands, and they appear to be isotropic near the Fermi level. It is worth to note that the band tuning was observed at the gamma point of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure. The gamma point band tuning for the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure is required to enhance the photocatalytic H_2 generation of the composite.

2.2. Density of states and electron localization function for the monolayer and heterostructure

To realize a comprehensive understanding of the electron contributions in both valence and conduction bands, the density of states calculations (Fig. 3a–c), including both total density of states and partial density of states, were conducted for the monolayer WS_2 , Ti_3C_2 and $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure. Pseudo-atomic calculations of valence electrons were performed for the all the components. For Ti_3C_2 and WS_2 monolayers, the calculations considered valence electrons of C ($2s^2 2p^2$), and Ti ($3s^2 3p^6 3d^2 4s^2$) and W ($5s^2 5p^6 5d^4 6s^2$) and S ($3s^2 3p^4$), correspondingly.

From the calculations (Fig. 3a), it was deduced that the highest valence band states have electron contributions, with a maximum of $3d_4$ electron contribution for the WS_2 monolayer. In contrast, the lowest valence band is mainly shaped by $5p_6$ -state electrons, resulting in minimal S atom contributions near the Fermi level. Nevertheless, in conduction bands, W- $3d_4$ orbitals are dominant and they play a crucial role in determining the electronic properties of WS_2 monolayer. For the Ti_3C_2 monolayer (Fig. 3b), the highest valence band at the fermi level indicates a contribution principally from the Ti- $3d_2$ state. Considering the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure (Fig. 3c), there is a strong hybridization

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure photocatalysts with band alignment.

Fig. 2. The calculated electronic band structure of (a) monolayer WS₂, (b) monolayer Ti₃C₂, and (c) WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure.

Fig. 3. Partial density of states plots depicting the distribution of electronic states along with an inset of electron localization function in (a) WS₂ monolayer, (b) Ti₃C₂ monolayer, and (c) WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure.

Fig. 4. The work functions of (a) WS₂ monolayer, (b) Ti₃C₂ monolayer and (c) WS₂/Ti₃C₂. The pink and green dashed lines represent the vacuum and Fermi level, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

between Ti-3d₂ and S-3p₄ states at the Fermi level. As a result of *p-d* hybridization, a gamma point band gap tuning takes place in the band structure of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure as demonstrated in Fig. 2c. Electron Localization Function (ELF) analysis offers a direct measure of electron localization, quantifying it within a range of 0–1. In Fig. 3(a–c) inset, ELF domains are visually represented by isosurfaces with an isovalue of 0.5. These visualizations allow us to observe changes in electron localization within the context of WS₂ (Fig. 3a inset), Ti₃C₂ (Fig. 3b inset) and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ (Fig. 3c inset). For monolayer WS₂, the domains remain distinct with no interconnected electron pathways between W and S atoms which lead to a band gap of 1.81 eV. In the case of Ti₃C₂, the hybridization of *d* and *p* orbital of Ti and C respectively occurs, where the *d* orbital is highly contributing near the Fermi level. In what concerns WS₂/Ti₃C₂, substantial deformations of both valence and core domains of S and Ti are induced, which brings them closer and creates interconnected pathways to facilitate electron mobility across the heterostructure due to the strong *p-d* hybridization. This certainly influences *p-d* hybridization on opening the energy gap in the position of the gamma point at the fermi level [48].

2.3. Work function of WS₂ monolayer, Ti₃C₂ monolayer and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure

The thermodynamic stability of electrons in the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure is deduced from the work function values. Typically, the band alignment and charge transfer at the interface of WS₂ and Ti₃C₂ in the

heterostructure is studied through the work function which is based on the equation below:

$$\Phi = E_{vac} - E_F$$

Where E_{vac} and E_F denote the energies of an electron in vacuum near the surface and Fermi level, respectively. Due to the mobility of electrons/upon contact in the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure, the electron chemical difference at the interface enables the electrons to migrate, which will occur until Fermi-level equilibration. It should be noted that the migration of electrons takes place from the component with low work function towards the component possessing a high work function. As a result, an induced electric field occurs at the interface, where the value increases from zero until the chemical potential difference between the heterostructure components tends to zero. The calculated work functions for monolayer WS₂, monolayer Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ are shown in Fig. 4a–c.

The work function for the monolayer WS₂ was found to be 5.579 eV (Fig. 4a), which is higher than the monolayers Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ at 4.355 eV and 4.064 eV (Fig. 4b and c), respectively. Considering the work function values, it is noted that the electrons in the monolayer Ti₃C₂ with a low work function of 4.355 eV migrate into the monolayer WS₂ surface with a high work function of 5.579 eV. This electron flow from Ti₃C₂ to WS₂ induces a potential energy at the interface and subsequent formation of Schottky barrier [49]. Moreover, the generated chemical potential difference from the Ti₃C₂ monolayer to WS₂ monolayer tends to minimize the charge diffusion, which is why the

Fig. 5. X-ray diffractograms, (a) WS₂, (b) Ti₃C₂ and (c) WS₂/Ti₃C₂ nanostructures.

WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure work function value was reduced to 4.064 eV (Fig. 4c). In addition, the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructures exhibited more stable and lower thermal conductivity due to the absence of imaginary modes in the phonon dispersion as shown in Fig. S2.

2.4. Morphological, optical, and band alignment of WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure

The distinctive structures and potential interactions in the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure were experimentally studied. WS₂, a member of 2D transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDC) family and Ti₃C₂, a member of the MXene family, exhibited characteristic patterns in X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman signatures and valence states in X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) that provide insight into their structural and chemical properties. The phase purity and formation of WS₂ (JCPDS #04-003-5636) and Ti₃C₂ (JCPDS #00-052-0875) nanostructures (Fig. 5a and b) was confirmed through the XRD studies. Further, the X-ray diffractogram portrayed in Fig. 5c validated the formation of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite nanostructure. Raman spectroscopy was utilized to investigate in more detail the structural and electronic characteristics, corroborating the formation of pure phase WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite nanostructures (Fig. S3). Raman spectra of MXene provided detailed information on their bonding and revealed the presence of surface terminations (-OH, -O, -F, etc.). The Raman mode around low-frequency region, ~120 cm⁻¹ is associated with the vibrations of titanium atoms with the carbon atoms in the lattice. The peak at 205 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the out-of-plane vibrations of Ti and C atoms. Similarly, the region around 600-700 cm⁻¹ represents the vibrations involving surface terminations such as Ti-O bonds or interactions with -OH groups. The Raman spectrum of WS₂ exhibits characteristic peaks at ~174, 194, 232, 297, 350 and 420 cm⁻¹, corresponding to specific vibrational modes.

In order to gain a better understanding of the elemental composition, chemical bonding and oxidation state of the elements present on the surface of the materials, XPS measurements was performed for the pristine WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ nanostructures. Fig. 6 represents the survey spectra of WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composites, verifying the presence of all the elements. The high resolution XPS spectra of the W 4f core level region (Fig. S4 (a)) in WS₂ illustrated the distinct peaks that could be deconvoluted into components corresponding to W 5p_{3/2}, W 4f_{3/2} and W 4f_{7/2} peaks at binding energies of ~38.08, 34.7, and 32.5 eV, respectively. Tungsten is mainly present in IV oxidation state within WS₂ lattice and only about 10 at.% of WO₃. Similarly, deconvoluted XPS spectra of the S 2p core level region (Fig. S4 (b)) displayed two dominant peaks at binding energies of 162.1 and 163.3 eV, which are attributed to S 2p_{1/2} and S 2p_{3/2} orbitals of S^{-II} oxidation state, confirming the existence of sulfide species in WS₂. Also, the peaks around binding energies 168.6 and 169.8 eV are assigned to a partially oxidized S on the particle

surface (VI oxidation state, ca. 12 at.%). It is worth to denote that the oxidized W and S sites are usually present on defects or edges.

Considering the XPS spectra of Ti₃C₂, the deconvoluted Ti 2p spectra revealed distinct peaks at binding energies of 454.8, 455.6, 456.8 and 458.8 eV which correspond to the various oxidation states transitioning from pure carbide to oxide as the oxidation number increases: Ti(I), Ti (II), Ti(III) and TiO₂, correspondingly (Fig. S4 (c)). Moreover, the XPS spectrum of C 1s (Fig. S4 (d)) consists of components representing Ti-C, C-C and C-O bonding states. The observation of strong Ti-C peaks, originating from C atoms within the interior of the Ti₃C₂ MXene nanolayers, signifies the characteristic and expected XPS spectrum of Ti₃C₂ [50]. Further, the XPS spectra of individual elements show only negligible changes after the formation of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite structure as depicted in Fig. (S4 (e-h)).

The morphological features of the as-synthesized WS₂/Ti₃C₂ materials were investigated through SEM imaging (Fig. 7a-c). Fig. 4a demonstrates that the exfoliated WS₂ possessed thin nanosheet structures of thickness about <1 μm. In addition, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) analysis revealed the presence of as-formed thin WS₂ nanoflakes. An average height of ~15 nm was derived through AFM imaging (Fig. S8). Further, upon leaching using HF treatment, the Ti₃AlC₂ precursor underwent a transformation with effective removal of the aluminium interlayer resulting in a distinctive accordion-like multilayer Ti₃C₂ structure characterized by flat surfaces and opened interspaces between the layers (Fig. 7b). The successful hybridization of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructures is indicated by the uniform dispersion of WS₂ nanosheets across the Ti₃C₂ MXene layers as depicted in Fig. 7c. It is worth to mention that the long range Ti₃C₂ layers are retained during the heterostructure formation. More details into the elemental composition of WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite were obtained from energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (Figs. S5-S7). The results of EDS validated the elemental compositions and confirmed the presence of tungsten disulfide (WS₂), titanium carbide (Ti₃C₂) and their combination in the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite material which agrees well with the XPS survey scans (Fig. 6). A decrease in the aluminium content of about 1.4% in Ti₃C₂ MXene demonstrates the effective removal of aluminium portions from the Ti₃AlC₂ MAX phase through HF etching. Furthermore, the elemental mapping of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure illustrated that the monolayers of WS₂ are randomly decorated over the Ti₃C₂ surfaces, which is rather essential to achieve interface-driven photocatalytic properties.

Fig. 7d presents the UV-Vis absorbance spectra of WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite, illustrating the optical properties, spin-orbit coupling effects and potential synergistic effects. Normally, the absorption spectra of Ti₃C₂ do not show any absorption edge due to its metallic nature. However, the as-synthesized Ti₃C₂ exhibits an absorption band around 300-350 nm region, ascribed to the inter-band transitions as supported by our theoretical calculations and earlier reports

Fig. 6. XPS survey spectra, (a) WS₂, (b) Ti₃C₂ and (c) WS₂/Ti₃C₂ nanostructures.

Fig. 7. Scanning Electron Microscopy images of (a) WS₂, (b) Ti₃C₂ and (c) Ti₃C₂/WS₂ composite materials; (d) UV-Vis absorbance spectra of WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and Ti₃C₂/WS₂ composite; (e) Calculated absorption spectra of: WS₂ monolayer, Ti₃C₂ monolayer and WS₂/Ti₃C₂; (f) Band alignment in Ti₃C₂/WS₂ heterostructure.

[51,52]. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of WS₂ exhibits four distinct absorption peaks with the size reduction of WS₂ to the nanoscale regime; these peaks are located approximately at 638 nm (1.94 eV), 530 nm (2.34 eV), 468 nm (2.65 eV) and 421 nm (2.95 eV) correspondingly.

The absorption peaks at 638 and 530 nm are attributed to excitonic absorption arising from direct gap transitions at the K point of the Brillouin zone with an energy separation around ~ 0.4 eV, arising from spin-orbit coupling (SOC)-induced splitting of the valence band at the K point. The peaks observed around 468 and 421 nm are assigned to direct optical transitions from deep valence band to the conduction band. Additionally, the presence of a small absorption peak around 275 nm reflects the quantum confinement effects due to the reduced size of WS₂ [53]. The WS₂/Ti₃C₂ light absorption showed a discernible increase in light absorption capacity due to the efficient charge transportation, which could boost photocatalytic processes.

In relation with experimental UV-Vis absorbance spectra, the photocatalytic activities of monolayer WS₂ and Ti₃C₂ as well as for the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure were theoretically calculated taking into account their optical properties as shown in Fig. 7e. The absorption edges of both monolayer WS₂ and Ti₃C₂ components occur at wavelengths $\lambda > 520$ nm, indicating their suitability as visible light semiconductor photocatalysts, which is essential for an efficient exploitation of solar radiation. Besides, the absorption edge of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure was found to be shifted to a broader wavelength region due to the coupled WS₂ and Ti₃C₂ components, contributing towards an enhanced absorption of visible light. Thus, it is evident that the strong hybridization of S-*p*₄ and Ti-*3d*₂ of monolayer WS₂ and Ti₃C₂ respectively enhances the optical absorption edge and intensity of Ti₃C₂ in the visible light region, leading to an improved photocatalytic activity for the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure. Photoinduced electron transfer strongly relies on the band edges of the photocatalyst material with reference to the redox potentials of the adsorbed molecules. Moreover, a schematic representation of photocatalytic H₂ generation mechanism is shown in Fig. 7f; upon irradiation of the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ catalyst, electrons are excited from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB) of WS₂, leaving the holes in the valence band intact. In the present case, the Schottky junction

formed at the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ interface facilitates the charge transfer thanks to the ultrathin metallic nature of Ti₃C₂ [54]. The photogenerated electrons are easily transferred to the CB of Ti₃C₂ resulting in the lowering of electron-hole recombination process. This lowering of the recombination stage endows availability of electrons and holes for water splitting.

2.5. Photo-electrochemical measurements

Photo-electrochemical (PEC) measurements provide valuable insights into the photo-electrochemical performance of materials for both hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER). The PEC curves of the WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ samples were initially determined by performing two-half reactions through cathodic and anodic scan linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) in 1 M KOH solution at a scan rate of 5 mV/s. Fig. 8a presents the LSV measurement to assess the photocatalytic activity of WS₂, Ti₃C₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite for the HER under chopped-light illumination (10s ON/5s OFF) at 420 nm wavelength.

The obtained LSV demonstrates enhanced catalytic activity for Ti₃C₂/WS₂ composite with low overpotential (η) of 92 mV, 186 mV and 260 mV at current densities of 100, 300 and 500 mA/cm² respectively, compared to pure Ti₃C₂ (235, 366, 468 mV at 100, 300, 500 mA/cm² correspondingly) and WS₂ (443, 564, 659 mV at 100, 300, 500 mA/cm² respectively). In addition, to better comprehend the influence of light on HER performance, irradiations from LED (light-emitting diode) sources with different wavelengths were employed (Fig. 8b). It was observed that the composite displayed an obvious change in the catalytic activity under dark condition and at distinct LED wavelengths, exhibiting lowest overpotential values when irradiated with a 420 nm LED source. A further study of the catalytic activity during anodic scan, which is a complicated four-electron process, revealed a remarkable OER activity under dark and light conditions. As noticed in Fig. 8c, the WS₂/Ti₃C₂ composite showed an improved OER activity upon irradiation using 420 nm LED light. Also, WS₂/Ti₃C₂ photoanodes display better catalytic activity with lower overpotential upon irradiation of 420 nm light

Fig. 8. Linear sweep voltammetry measurements. (a–b) Photocatalytic HER process. (c–d) photocatalytic OER process. (a,c) HER and OER for WS_2 , Ti_3C_2 and $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ composite under illumination using 420 nm LED source, respectively and (b,d) $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ composite without and with light irradiation at different wavelengths of the illumination source, correspondingly.

compared to other LED wavelengths or dark condition (Fig. 8d). The $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ photoanode delivered an overpotential of 430, 570 and 690 mV at 100, 300 and 500 mA/cm^2 respectively when compared to Ti_3C_2 (690, 840 and 930 mV at 100, 300 and 500 mA/cm^2) and WS_2 monolayer (650, 820 and 900 mV at 100, 300 and 500 mA/cm^2) components.

2.6. Photocurrent density response

To comprehensively evaluate the photocurrent density response of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ catalyst to light (420 nm LED), chronoamperometry measurements were employed. This involved monitoring the effects of light addition and removal (20 s ON/20 s OFF) at a constant applied voltage of -0.1 V versus RHE in the HER region and at $+1.6$ V versus RHE in the OER region, as illustrated in Fig. 9. The transient photocurrent response of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ catalyst was further assessed upon irradiation with varying LED wavelengths ranging from 385 to 500 nm (Fig. 9c). Several different photocurrent intensities for the 420 nm LED were also examined, as depicted in Fig. 9d.

Remarkably, it was observed that the composite $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ catalyst demonstrated increased photocurrent densities of ~ 33 and 120 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ upon irradiation with 420 nm LED in the HER and OER region. Indeed, this photocurrent density exhibited by the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ photocatalyst is notably superior when compared to other reported 2D photocatalysts, particularly surpassing previously reported MXene/ TiO_2 - WS_2 based-catalysts [49,55]. This suggests the efficacy of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ catalyst in harnessing light energy for enhanced catalytic activity across a broad

range of wavelengths, particularly at 420 nm, and toward an improved photogenerated carrier separation efficiency. Another effective criterion that should be used to evaluate a catalyst is its long-term stability under selected electrochemical conditions.

As shown in Fig. 10 (a), the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ nanostructure not only displayed excellent HER and OER activity but also a long-term stability with a good overall water splitting ability. At a current density of 100 mA/cm^2 (Fig. 10 (b)), the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2 \parallel \text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ nanostructures exhibited an excellent catalytic stability over 80 h at around ~ 1.82 V vs RHE. The noticeable robustness of the $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ nanocomposite holds significant promise as an efficient catalyst for sustainable hydrogen and oxygen generation.

Further, to gain information on the composition and electronic properties of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ nanostructures post catalytic activity, the recovered electrocatalyst was studied through ex-situ XPS (Fig. 11). The acquired spectra corroborated the presence of the anticipated elements, Ti, C, W and S (Fig. 11(a–e)). In the case of WS_2 , the sample tested showed excellent stability with partial oxidation to WO_2 . Formation of higher oxide WO_3 could not be excluded, because of overlapping with broad K3s peak from the electrolyte. However, peak area of K3s matched amount of potassium determined from K2p. Although high-resolution XPS spectra of Ti 2p core level region revealed the formation of titanium dioxide (TiO_2) on the top layers of composite, the emergence of TiO_2 did not apparently compromise the performance of the composite towards the OER. To assess the impact of the stability test on the charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of the electrode, electrochemical impedance

Fig. 9. Chronoamperometry photoreponse measurement of WS_2/Ti_3C_2 composite under 420 nm LED light irradiation at, (a) -0.1 V versus RHE in the HER region and (b) $+1.6$ V versus RHE in the OER region. Chronoamperometry photocurrent density measurement of WS_2/Ti_3C_2 composite under illumination using, (c) LED sources with different irradiation wavelengths and (d) 420 nm LED source by varying the current intensity.

Fig. 10. Chronopotentiometric plot of WS_2/Ti_3C_2 nanostructures.

spectroscopy (EIS) was employed. The Nyquist plots shown in Fig. S9 reveal a minimal change in electrode resistance, with pre-test and post-test values of approximately 10 and 14 Ω , respectively.

The above results suggest that the WS_2/Ti_3C_2 nanocomposite retains excellent charge transfer kinetics even after undergoing the stability evaluation for long duration. The PEC measurements confirm that the composite material, consisting of Ti_3C_2 and WS_2 showed an enhanced

photocatalytic performance compared to the individual components [56,57]. Insightful understanding through the obtained theoretical and experimental results reveals that the synergistic effects and interface engineering of Ti_3C_2/WS_2 are responsible for its brilliant catalytic activity; the electron flow from Ti_3C_2 to WS_2 induces a chemical potential at the interface which certainly minimizes the charge diffusion, thus boosting the catalytic performance.

Fig. 11. XPS spectra of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ composite after stability measurement. (a) Survey scan, (b) W, (c) Ti, (d) S, and (e) C, respectively.

3. Conclusions

In this work, first principles calculations was adopted to study the structural, electronic and optical properties of monolayers of tungsten disulfide (WS_2), titanium carbide (Ti_3C_2) MXene and $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ heterostructure. From the theoretical calculations, we understand that the strong p - d hybridization at the interface of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ nanocomposite triggers the subsequent formation of Schottky barrier which can improve the photocatalytic activity. The successfully synthesized Ti_3C_2 MXene/ WS_2 nanocomposite exhibits significantly enhanced photocatalytic hydrogen evolution. In addition, the as-synthesized hybrid nanocomposite demonstrated desirable photocatalytic H_2 production with photocurrent densities of ~ 33 and $120 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ in the HER and OER regions respectively, under light irradiation using an LED source of a 420 nm wavelength. The formation of excellent hetero-interface between the WS_2 and Ti_3C_2 layers was found to facilitate effective separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs with reduced rate of carrier recombination, leading to a higher density of charge carriers available for catalytic reactions. Detailed mechanisms governing the superb photocatalytic performance shed light on the potential applications of the presented material in renewable energy conversion and environmental sustainability.

4. Methodology

4.1. Theoretical calculations

All the Density functional theory calculations were performed using CASTEP (Cambridge Sequential Total Energy Package code) in Materials Studio which uses the planewave basis set [58]. The interactions between the ion cores and the valence electrons for Ti_3C_2 , as well as for WS_2 , were treated using the norm-conserving pseudopotential [59]. To prevent any exchange and correlation effects, the generalised gradient approximation in the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof functionals was used [60]. All the geometrical structures were fully relaxed until the

convergence criteria of the force and energy tolerance were lower than $0.01 \text{ eV } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ and 10^{-6} eV , respectively, with a self-consistent convergence accuracy of 10^{-6} eV per atom. To control the electronic minimization algorithm, tolerance factor was used as a medium. All parameters were examined without applying pressure and kept at zero. The maximum force is constant at $0.05 \text{ eV}/\text{\AA}$. To determine accurate electronic structures for WS_2 , Ti_3C_2 and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure systems, electronic eigenvalues along high symmetry directions in the Brillouin zone were calculated. The cutoff energy has been set at 450 eV. The optical absorption spectra of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ vdWs heterostructures was determined using the frequency-dependent dielectric function.

4.2. Experimental section

Fabrication of Ti_3C_2 MXene: Ti_3C_2 MXene was synthesized using a traditional procedure involving the use of hydrofluoric acid (HF). To initiate the synthesis of MXene, 25 g of Ti_3AlC_2 MAX material (Jinzhou Haixin Metal Materials, China) was suspended in a solution of 250 mL of 40 wt% HF cooled on 0°C (Penta, Czech Republic). The mixture was continuously stirred under ambient conditions for one week. Following chemical exfoliation, the mixture was subjected to decantation, repeated centrifugation and water dispersion cycles until the residual water reached a neutral pH value. The chemically exfoliated MXene (5 g) was dispersed in 100 mL of 20 wt% tetrabutylammonium hydroxide and stirred at room temperature for one week and the subsequently delaminated MXene was separated by repeated centrifugation and dispersion in water. Finally, the MXene was separated and stored in ethanol.

Fabrication of WS_2 nanosheets: To synthesize WS_2 nanosheets, a suspension of bulk WS_2 (99%, Sigma Aldrich, Czech Republic) in a mixture of deionized water and isopropyl alcohol (1:1) at a concentration of 5 mg/mL was subjected to high pressure microfluidic exfoliation by ultrasonication (100 W, 30 min). Afterwards, the WS_2 dispersion was passed through 0.1 mm diamond microfluidic channel for 30 times under a pressure of 200 MPa, further breaking down the WS_2 aggregates

and promoting the exfoliation of WS₂ layers into uniform thinner nanosheets.

Fabrication of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure: The preparation of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ hybrid structures involved mixing of exfoliated WS₂ nanosheets with Ti₃C₂ nanosheets followed by ultrasonication to achieve a uniformly dispersed composite structure. Typically, 1 mL of exfoliated WS₂ suspension was mixed with 2 mL of Ti₃C₂ and further subjected to ultrasonication for about 3 h to disperse the nanosheets evenly throughout the suspension and promote interactions between the WS₂ and Ti₃C₂ components.

4.3. Characterization techniques

The crystal structure and phase purity of the samples were investigated using Bruker D8 Discoverer X-ray diffractometer (XRD) employing Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) under standard operating conditions (40 kV, 40 mA). Raman spectroscopy characterization was conducted using inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, England) equipped with a charge-coupled device detector (CCD). The excitation source for the analysis was a diode-pumped solid-state (DPSS) laser operating at a wavelength of 532 nm. The surface composition of the samples was further studied with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using SPECS spectrometer equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (1486.7 eV) and a hemispherical electron analyzer Phoibos 150. Survey XPS spectra were recorded with Ep set to 100 eV, whereas the high-resolution spectra of the core lines were acquired with Ep set to 20 eV. The base chamber pressure during the measurements was at 10⁻⁹ mbar or lower. Samples were placed on conductive Cu tape. Low-energy electron (1–3 eV) flood gun was used to compensate the surface charging during the XPS spectra acquisition. The morphology and elemental mapping of the fabricated materials were examined utilizing a scanning electron microscope coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) (Tescan Lyra 3, Czech Republic). Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) analyses were performed using a Tescan MAIA 3 system with a beam voltage of 30 kV. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements were carried out to determine the thickness of the exfoliated nanostructures. A FlexAFM™ instrument equipped with C3000 controller from Nanosurf™ was utilized. Ultraviolet–visible (UV–Vis) spectra were recorded using a LAMBDA 850+ UV/Vis spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer in the United States) in the scan range 250–800 nm. Photo-electrochemical characterization of the materials was performed using a Metrohm autolab PGSTAT 204 (NOVA Version 2.1.5, Utrecht, Netherlands) electrochemical workstation. The measurements were conducted under both dark and illuminated conditions to evaluate the photo-electrochemical activity via running linear sweep voltammograms (LSV, scan rate of 5 mV/s) and chronoamperometry measurements using various LED sources. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted using a frequency range of 0.1 Hz–100 kHz at an amplitude of 10 mV. In this photo-electrochemical experiment, a 3-electrode system was utilized, consisting of a working electrode, a reference electrode, and a counter electrode with 1 M potassium hydroxide (KOH) as electrolyte solution. The working electrode was prepared by coating nickel foam with the desired material. A mercury/mercury oxide (Hg/HgO) electrode served as the reference electrode, while a carbon rod was employed as the counter electrode.

Data availability

The datasets generated and/or analyzed in this study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/13692237>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Amutha Subramani: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal

analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Levna Chacko:** Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Bing Wu:** Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Vlastimil Mazánek:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Chenrayan Senthil:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Stefanos Mourdikoudis:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Zdeněk Sofer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtsust.2024.100964>.

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